

INCONGRUENT RESISTANCE TO AMINOGLYCOSIDES IN MULTIDRUG-RESISTANT MYCOBACTERIUM TUBERCULOSIS STRAINS

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ABSTRACT

Since the discovery of the bactericidal activity of aminoglycosides, streptomycin, kanamycin, amikacin, and capreomycin (a macrocyclic peptide) have been widely used to treat tuberculosis and multidrug-resistant (MDR) tuberculosis. In general practice, resistance to kanamycin is often used as the sole criterion for defining extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis, assuming that all other drugs in this group or related drugs are resistant to certain strains. However, the assumption of cross-resistance between drugs in the same group is not always true for Mycobacterium tuberculosis. This prompted us to conduct a study to determine the concordance resistance pattern between aminoglycosides and the macrocyclic peptide capreomycin. A total of 2383 mycobacterial strains isolated from suspected MDR cases were subjected to susceptibility testing with aminoglycosides (kanamycin and amikacin), the polypeptide capreomycin, and ofloxacin to determine the resistance pattern. Cultures and susceptibility testing were performed using an automated BACTEC MGIT 960 instrument. Positive susceptibility samples were confirmed by PCR. The results showed that, of the total 2383 strains, 844 (35.41%) were susceptible to all four drugs, and 1539 (64.58%) strains showed resistance in the form of multi- or mono-resistance. The results also showed that of the 474 kanamycin-resistant mycobacterial strains, 86.7% and 77.6% were resistant to amikacin and capreomycin, respectively. Conversely, of the 425 amikacin-resistant mycobacterial strains, 3.3% were susceptible to kanamycin. Our findings suggest that performing susceptibility testing for individual drugs within a class may not provide an accurate strain status and may not be sufficient to make clinical decisions. It is necessary to conduct susceptibility testing of all MDR-TB strains with all aminoglycoside and macrocyclic peptide drugs before subjecting patients to comprehensive drug therapy.

Keyword: Aminoglycoside drug Multidrug resistant tuberculosis, concordance.

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) remains one of the most common causes of human death from a single infectious agent. The bacterium Mycobacterium tuberculosis is estimated to have infected a quarter of the

world's population, although it can remain in latent form in the body for a lifetime. About 90% of all patients who develop TB symptoms each year are adults. By 2021, an estimated 10.6 million people were infected with tuberculosis, resulting in more than 1.6 million deaths worldwide (Houben& Dodd, 2016).

Aminoglycoside drugs, especially Streptomycin, are key medicine for treating primary tuberculosis during the intensive phase. With the emergence of multidrug resistance tuberculosis (MDR-TB) other important aminoglycoside drugs have also been included in the treatment regimen (Houben& Dodd, 2016). The incidence of MDR-TB is the highest ever recorded in nearly 90 countries, accounting for an estimated 5% of all TB infections worldwide. Additionally, extensively drug-resistant TB (XDR TB) cases have been confirmed in 58 countries (Tsukamura& Mizuno, 1975, Georghiou et al., 2012) India accounts for 2.3 million of the world's estimated 8.6 million annual tuberculosis cases, with 99,000 instances of MDR TB (Reeves et al., 2013) (Reeves et al., 2013). The emergence of MDR and XDR-TB and their different treatment pose a challenge to the Indian TB eradication program, in which Kanamycin, amikacin and capreomycin are the main drugs used in the intensive phase of treatment MDR-TB for 6-9 months.

In India, the Programmatic Management of Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis (PMDT) guidelines recommend susceptibility testing for two drugs, Kanamycin and Ofloxacin, during the treatment of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB). Due to cross-resistance phenomena, all drugs in the same group tend to have similar resistance and susceptibility patterns. Therefore, if strains are resistant to Kanamycin, they are likely to be resistant to the other two drugs in the group, namely Amikacin and Capreomycin. However, it has been observed that many mycobacterial strains resistant to Kanamycin are not resistant to Amikacin or Capreomycin (Guidelines on Programmatic Management of Drug Resistant TB (PMDT) in India Central TB Division, 2012, WHO report, 2011). Before any clinical conclusions are drawn, it is essential to consider the results of the susceptibility tests for Kanamycin, Amikacin, and Capreomycin. The purpose of this study was to investigate the degree of resistance to Kanamycin, Amikacin, and Capreomycin, as well as any cross-resistance that may exist.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Processing of the samples and BACTEC MGIT 960 liquid media

The study was conducted between August 2016 and January 2017 at the National Institute of TB and RD in New Delhi. Study was approved by ethical committee of Institute having ethical NITRD/EC/07 dated 01.04.2015.

Sputum samples were collected according to national guidelines. Samples from patients clinically suspected of having TB were sent to the microbiology laboratory for culture and drug susceptibility testing. Sputum was then examined under a smear microscope, cultured using the Bactec Mycobacterium Growth Indicator Tube (MGIT)-960 system, and further tested using the MGIT direct smear test (DST). All MDR strains were additionally tested with kanamycin, amikacin, and capreomycin to determine the resistance pattern and percentage of cross-resistance between kanamycin, amikacin, and capreomycin. Susceptibility testing with the aminoglycoside's kanamycin, amikacin, the polypeptide capreomycin, and ofloxacin was performed on a total of 2383 mycobacterial strains isolated from suspected MDR cases. The automated instrument BACTEC MGIT 960 was used to perform sensitivity tests and cultures (Becton Dickinson, USA-BD).

Molecular analysis of drug-resistant gene:

In selected cases, the discordant resistant strains were further analyzed by amplification and sequencing of the *rrs*, *eis*, and *tly* genes at the Center for Bio-Design & Diagnostics (CBD) Translational Health Science and Technology Institute, Faridabad, Haryana. Briefly, growth from LJ media was dissolved in 500 µl TE buffer and heat-activated at 80 °C for 20 minutes. The heat-inactivated tube was centrifuged at 6000xg at 4 °C for 10 minutes. The precipitate was resuspended in 400 µl of Tris-EDTA-Tween lysozyme solution and incubated at 37 °C for 3 hours. To the treated sample, SDS 1% (w/v) and Proteinases K 1 mg/ml were added and incubated for 1 hour at 37 °C. After incubation, 80 µl of 5 M NaCl and 80 µl of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) (Sigma, USA) were added to the suspension, and the tubes were heated at 65 °C for 15 minutes. An equal volume of chloroform-isoamyl alcohol (24:1) (v/v) was then added to the suspension.

The DNA was separated from the aqueous phase and placed in another tube, and the step was repeated one more time. The DNA was then precipitated by adding 0.1 volumes of 3 M sodium acetate (pH 5.3) and 2.5 volumes of ice-cooled absolute ethanol, followed by incubation at -70 °C for 30 minutes. The DNA mixture was centrifuged at 12,000xg for 15 minutes at 4 °C, and the DNA precipitate was dissolved in 50 µl TE buffer for PCR. Amplification of the above genes was performed using previously published primers (Engstrom et al., 2011).

PCR cycling conditions consisted of a 5-min denaturation at 94 °C followed by 35 cycles of 30-sec denaturation at 94 °C, 1-min annealing at 56-60 °C, and 1-2-min extension at 72 °C, depending on the size of the PCR product. PCR products were detected by agarose gel electrophoresis and purified using the QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, Germany). BigDye Terminator v3.1 (Applied Biosystems) was used to sequence the purified products. Sequencing reads were analyzed using the FASTA-N program

RESULTS

In this study, 2383 clinical isolates were subjected to susceptibility testing with the MGIT 960 system to kanamycin, amikacin, capreomycin, and ofloxacin. The susceptibility testing revealed 11 different resistance patterns. The overall results showed that 35.4% of the mycobacterial strains were sensitive to all 4 drugs and 64.6% had resistance in the form of multi- or monodrug resistance patterns. Of the resistant patterns, 13.6% of the strains showed resistance to all four drugs, i.e., kanamycin, amikacin, and capreomycin, as well as ofloxacin, the most common resistance pattern observed in this study. Other common resistance patterns observed during the study were 3-drug resistant mycobacterial strains, i.e., kanamycin, amikacin, and ofloxacin, which were observed in 1.8% of mycobacterial strains. For the 2-drug combination, 1.8% of mycobacterial strains were resistant to kanamycin and ofloxacin, 0.92% to capreomycin and ofloxacin, 0.25% to kanamycin and amikacin, 0.25% to amikacin and ofloxacin, and 0.04% to kanamycin and capreomycin (Table-1).

In the pattern of mono-resistance, kanamycin was the most frequently detected drug (0.58%) among the 3 injectable drugs tested (Table 2). The results showed that of the total 474 kanamycin-resistant mycobacterial strains, 86.7% were resistant to amikacin and 77.6% to capreomycin. Of the 395 capreomycin-resistant strains, 91.4% were resistant to both kanamycin and amikacin, while 24 (6.07%) strains were sensitive to both antibiotics. Of the 425 amikacin-resistant mycobacterial strains, 3.3% were sensitive to kanamycin. Further analysis showed that 7 (1.77%) mycobacterial

strains resistant to capreomycin and kanamycin were also sensitive to amikacin, and 3 (0.75%) strains resistant to capreomycin and amikacin were also sensitive to kanamycin (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

In this study, we investigated the resistance pattern of aminoglycosides and the macrocyclic peptide capreomycin. Several previous studies have repeatedly shown a high degree of cross-resistance as well as inconsistent resistance between amikacin and kanamycin and even with capreomycin ([www.tbcindia.org/ Lab Manual](http://www.tbcindia.org/LabManual), 1999, Alangaden et al., 1998, Heifets, 1991). These drugs have been considered interchangeable for drug susceptibility testing. The results of our study contradict the general concept of cross-resistance between drugs of the same group (Sugawara et al., 2009) found that 80% of kanamycin-resistant strains were resistant to amikacin, which is comparable to our study in which 86.7% of 474 kanamycin-resistant strains were resistant to amikacin (15). In another study by (Jugheli et al., 2008), 53.8% of the total mycobacterial strains were resistant to kanamycin, whereas in our study 19.9% of the strains were resistant to kanamycin. The conflicting results between kanamycin and amikacin were observed who showed that a total of 11.5% of kanamycin-resistant strains were sensitive to amikacin, which is very similar to our study. Cross-resistance between kanamycin and capreomycin was also demonstrated by (Jugheli et al., 2008) who found that 20.5% of kanamycin-resistant strains were sensitive to capreomycin (Sugawara et al., 2009). In comparison, our study showed that of 474 kanamycin-resistant strains, 77.6% were resistant to capreomycin. This difference could be due to the different methodologies (Krüüner et al., 2003), demonstrated that 54% of kanamycin-resistant Estonian mycobacterial strains were sensitive to amikacin. The same study emphasized that it may be necessary to test the resistance of *M. tuberculosis* isolates to both drugs because not all kanamycin-resistant mycobacterial strains are also resistant to amikacin. We have also seen that kanamycin and amikacin have very different rates of resistance.

CONCLUSION

This study suggests that parallel resistance between kanamycin/amikacin or kanamycin/capreomycin when performing susceptibility testing for a single drug in a class may not provide accurate strain status and may not be sufficient to make a clinical decision. The pattern of cross-resistance is not a uniform phenomenon, and variations occur when strains are tested with other drugs even though they belong to the same class. Genetic studies are needed to support our findings.

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Table 1: Multi - drug resistance profile of 2nd line injectable drug in multidrug resistant mycobacterial strains (N=2383)

s.no	Resistance pattern	Total number	Percentage (%) of resistance
1	All sensitive	844	35.41
Resistant to all 4 drugs (n=324)			
2	Kanamycin, amikacin, capreomycin and ofloxacin	324	13.59
Resistant to 3 drugs combination (n=90)			
3	Kanamycin, amikacin and ofloxacin	44	1.84
4	Kanamycin, amikacin, capreomycin	37	1.55
5	Kanamycin, capreomycin and ofloxacin	06	0.25
6	Amikacin, capreomycin and ofloxacin	03	0.12
Resistant to 2 drugs combination (n=77)			
7	Kanamycin, ofloxacin	42	1.76
8	Capreomycin, ofloxacin	22	0.92
9	Kanamycin, amikacin	06	0.25
10	Amikacin, ofloxacin	06	0.25
11	Kanamycin, capreomycin	01	0.04
	Total	1335	

Table 2: Mono- drug resistance pattern of 2nd line ATT drugs in suspected MDR patients (N=1048)

S.No	Resistance pattern	Total number	Percentage of resistance
1	Ofloxacin	1027	43.09
2	Kanamycin	14	0.58
3	Amikacin	05	0.02
4	Capreomycin	02	0.08
	Total	1048	

Table 3: Number of resistant isolates in relation to kanamycin Between amikacin and capreomycin

Antibiotics		Amikacin		capreomycin	
		Resistant	Sensitive	Resistant	Sensitive
Kanamycin	Resistant	411	63	368	106
	Sensitive	14	1895	27	1882